

THE NON-DESTRUCTIVE TESTING OF HONEYCOMB STRUCTURES BY THE COIN-TAP TECHNIQUE

P. Cawley
Dept Mechanical Engineering
Imperial College of Science and Technology
London SW7 2BX

and

R.D. Adams
Dept Mechanical Engineering
University of Bristol
Bristol BS8 1TR

ABSTRACT

The use of an automated version of the coin-tap method of non-destructive testing on honeycomb panels with CFRP skins has been investigated. The test involves tapping the structure in the region to be inspected with an instrumented hammer and recording the time history of the force applied to the structure during the impulse. The Fourier transform of the force pulse is then compared with that obtained on a area of the structure which is known to be good. The major advantage of the method is that no couplant is required between the structure and the tapping head. The technique is therefore particularly attractive for use in the field, and on honeycomb structures with thin skins which may be porous. It has been shown that the method can reliably detect defects smaller than 10 mm in diameter under 1 mm thick CFRP skins. This sensitivity is somewhat better than that obtained with the mechanical impedance method, and it has been shown that the coin-tap test is more reliable on thin structures than the mechanical impedance technique.

INTRODUCTION

The coin-tap test is one of the oldest methods of non-destructive testing and it is regularly used for testing laminated structures, honeycomb constructions and bonded joints. The test requires an operator to tap each point of the structure to be inspected with a coin, and to listen to the resulting sound radiated by the structure. It is found that defective regions sound 'dead', and can therefore be identified. Until recently, the test has remained largely subjective and there has been considerable uncertainty about the physical principles behind it. However, it has been widely used, and Hagemmaier and Fassbender [1] found that it could detect more types of defect in honeycomb constructions than any other technique except neutron radiography. Hart-Smith and Thrall [2] have also recommended its use for the inspection of adhesive joints.

It should be stressed that this test is quite different from the 'wheel-tap' test which was traditionally carried out to detect cracked railway wheels and defective pottery and glassware [3], though the testing technique and subjective interpretation of the sound produced is similar in both cases. The wheel-tap test is a global test which investigates the whole component from a tap applied at a single point, the difference between good and defective components being detected from changes in the natural frequencies and damping. The coin-tap test will only find defects in the region of the tap, so it is necessary to tap each part of the structure under investigation.

The sound produced when a structure is tapped is mainly at the frequencies of the major structural modes of vibration. These modes are structural properties which are essentially independent of the position of excitation. Therefore, if the same impulse is applied to a good area and to an adjacent defective area, the sound produced must be very similar. The difference in the sound produced when good and defective areas are tapped must therefore be due to a change in the local force input.

When a structure is struck with a hammer, the characteristics of the impact are dependent on the local impedance of the structure and on the hammer used. Damage such as an adhesive disbond results in a local decrease in the structural stiffness, and hence a change in the nature of the impact. This is illustrated in Fig 1a which shows measured force-time histories from taps on good and disbonded regions of a honeycomb structure with carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) skins. The impact over the good area is more intense and of shorter duration than that on the damaged area.

Figure 1a. Force-time histories of impacts on good and disbonded areas of CFRP skinned honeycomb structure.

Figure 1b. Spectra of time histories shown in Figure 1a.

The difference in the sound produced by the two taps may be explained by studying the frequency content of the two force pulses. This is achieved by carrying out a Fourier transform of the force-time records to produce the spectra shown in Fig 1b. The amplitude of the force input to the damaged area falls off rapidly with increasing frequency, while the impact on the sound area has a much lower rate of decrease of force with frequency. This means that the impact on the defective area will not excite the higher structural modes as strongly as the impact on the good zone. Therefore the sound produced does not contain the higher frequencies and the structure sounds duller.

These findings, which were originally reported in Reference 3, show that it is possible to produce a version of the coin-tap test which depends on the measurement of the force input to the test structure during the tap, rather than on the measurement of the sound produced by the tap. This has the advantage that the measurements are insensitive to background noise, and it is readily possible to produce an instrument which will apply a controlled impulse to a structure via an instrumented hammer and compare either the time history or frequency spectrum of the measured pulse with a standard obtained on a structure which is known to be good.

Ideally, the measure obtained when there is no defect present would not vary with position on the structure so that a single standard could be used for all regions of a component. However, in practice, some variation with position in a good structure is seen, particularly when the structure has a low rigidity [4]. It is therefore necessary to define a criterion which will minimise this variation.

There are many possible ways of comparing the time histories and/or spectra of two impacts. Three obvious candidates are comparisons of peak force, impact duration and rate of decrease of force with frequency in the middle of the frequency range shown in Fig 1b. However, all these possibilities have serious drawbacks.

If peak force were to be used, it would be essential to ensure very accurate control of the velocity of the hammer immediately prior to impact, otherwise a standard velocity impact on a good region could be confused with a higher velocity impact over a defect. In practice, it is likely to be difficult to provide sufficiently accurate control, particularly if the hammer is to operate in different orientations. The work described in Reference 4 showed that a test based on impact duration or rate of decrease of force with frequency at a particular frequency would also tend to be unreliable.

All the possibilities discussed above seek to detect the presence of a defect by using only a very small proportion of the data which is available if the time history of the impact force is measured. Not only does this discard potentially valuable information, but it makes the result very sensitive to random noise on critical data points. Several possible methods for overcoming these difficulties have been investigated, the most satisfactory one to be devised being illustrated in Fig 2. This involves obtaining the spectrum of the force pulse which, with the advent of dedicated Fourier transform micro-chips, is a simple and very rapid procedure. The areas A and B under the logarithmic graph of the spectrum shown in Fig 2a are then calculated. The ratio, R, defined by

$$R = B/(A+B) \quad (1)$$

is then computed. Impacts over defects have lower high frequency force content than impacts over good areas, and so the value of R is reduced.

Figure 2a. Areas A and B used in comparison of test spectra with standard.

Figure 2b. Normalisation procedure used in comparison.

The frequency, f_b , at which the boundary between regions A and B is set is arbitrary, but 30 to 50 % of the full scale frequency, f_{max} , when the first minimum in the spectrum of an impact over a good region occurs close to the full scale frequency has been shown to be a satisfactory choice. The effect on the calculation of changes in the impact force is accounted for by normalising the results so that the zero frequency level on the two spectra to be compared is the same. Thus, if curve S in Fig 2b is a standard curve from a good area, and curve T is the result of a test, curve T is shifted to T' before the calculation is performed. The minimum force level to be included in the calculation is 30 dB below the value of the spectrum at zero frequency. In practice, this range is sufficient to include most of the measured data, and avoids any problems with random noise on the force signal.

Reference 4 reports an initial investigation of the technique involving theoretical predictions and tests on metal structures with simulated defects. As Hagemaijer and Fassbender [1] observed, the technique is very attractive for use on honeycomb structures, and this paper reports an initial investigation of the sensitivity of the technique on this type of structure.

TEST SPECIMENS

Three honeycomb specimens which were used in a study of the mechanical impedance method of non-destructive testing [5,6] were tested. The skins were either four or eight layer cross-plyed CFRP giving thicknesses of 0.5 and 1 mm respectively. Two of the specimens had 20 mm thick Nomex honeycomb cores, one having 8 layer skins and the other 4 layer skins. The third specimen had a 3 mm thick aluminium honeycomb core and 4 layer skins. The honeycomb cell diameter was approximately 6 mm in all the specimens. The skins were bonded to the honeycomb with a film adhesive, disbands of different sizes being introduced by removing areas of the film

before insertion into the joint. In order to test the method on defects formed by the adhesive layer failing to bond to the skin, rather than being absent altogether, two areas of adhesive were cut out from the film, pre-cured and bonded to the honeycomb before bonding the skin to the core. Two defects were deliberately placed close to the edges of the specimen so that the possibility of edge effects could be investigated. All the defects were in one face of the specimen, and the positions of the defects were the same in all the panels. A map of the defect types and positions is shown in Fig 3.

Figure 3. Map of defect locations in honeycomb panels. Defects 2e and 3e near edges, and defects 1a, 2a and 3a away from the edges were formed by omitting the adhesive layer. Defects 1p and 2p were formed by pre-curing the adhesive layer to the honeycomb.

TEST PROCEDURE

The system used to test the components was the same as that described in Reference 4. Essentially it consisted of a small, solenoid-actuated hammer (mass 65 gm) with a force gauge incorporated in its head. The hammer was mounted in a cylindrical holder which was rested on the structure to be tested, and so maintained a fixed distance between the structure surface and the striker in its rest position. When the solenoid was energised by a voltage pulse, the striker was accelerated towards the structure surface. The force signal produced by the impact was captured by a B & K Type 2032 spectrum analyser, and was passed to a micro-computer for further processing. It should be emphasised that this relatively complex testing system is only necessary for research purposes: a much simpler configuration is employed on the commercial instrument which has now been developed.

Tests were carried out in several good areas of each structure and over the middle of each of the defects. (Defect 3e was not investigated in these tests as its centre was only about 5 mm from the edge of the panels, which made it difficult to test with the striker design used here. This problem could readily be overcome by modifying the design.)

RESULTS

Fig 4a shows the force-time histories obtained from tests in a good area of the 20 mm thick honeycomb panel with 8 layer skins and above the 50 mm (1a), 20 mm (2a) and 10 mm (3a) diameter defects, the corresponding spectra being shown in Fig 4b. The results of all the tests on this panel are summarised in Table 1 which shows the peak force, impact duration and ratio, R , defined by equation (1) and Fig 2, the maximum frequency, f_{\max} , being 2 kHz and f_b being 0.6 kHz, at each test position.

Figure 4a. Force-time histories of impacts on good and defective areas of 20 mm thick honeycomb structure with 8 layer skins.

Figure 4b. Spectra of time histories shown in Figure 4a.

Fig 4a shows that, as expected, the impact duration increases as the defect severity increases, and that the peak force tends to decrease. However, the peak force above the good area is lower than that above the 10 mm diameter defect, 3a. This is simply because the impact velocity in this test was slightly lower than normal, and illustrates the danger referred to above of using peak force measurements as an indicator of damage. Table 1 shows that in other tests over good areas, the peak force was higher than that measured over the defects. In good areas away from the edges of the panel, there was little variation in either the impact duration or the ratio, R , and it is clear from Table 1 that impacts above each of the defects give ratios, R , which are lower than those obtained over good areas away from the edges of the panel, so the defects may reliably be detected. There is more variation close to the edges of the panel (the variation becomes significant within about 20 mm of the edge) and defect detection in this region becomes more difficult. Defect 2e shows a higher value of R than a good area close to the edge; this is merely indicative of the variability seen close to the edges.

Table 2 shows the results obtained on the 20 mm thick panel with 4 layer skins. In this case, the rate of decrease of force amplitude with frequency over good areas was somewhat higher than that shown in Fig 4b, so the ratio, R , was computed with $f_{\max} = 1200$ Hz and $f_D = 600$ Hz. On this panel, all the defects gave values of R which were substantially lower than those seen in the good areas, and so the defects could reliably be detected. The result from the one test which was carried out over a good area close to the edge of the panel is similar to that obtained in good areas in the middle of the panel, which may suggest that edge effects are less prevalent in panels with thinner skins. However, the predictions of Reference 4, together with the results obtained with

TABLE 1.
Results from 20 mm thick specimen with 8 layer skins

Position	Peak Force (N)	Pulse Duration (m sec)	Ratio, R. ($f_{\max} = 2$ kHz, $f_b = 0.6$ kHz)
GM	67	0.74	0.63
GE	33	0.87	0.53
LGM	55	0.78	0.63
1a	41	1.18	0.43
1p	64	0.98	0.56
2a	55	0.90	0.54
2p	61	0.84	0.58
2e	32	0.99	0.57
3a	61	0.84	0.59

GM : Mean of 5 tests in good areas away from edge.

GE : Test approximately 10 mm from edge.

LGM : Test on good area away from edge with results nearest to those above defects (i.e. minimum peak force, maximum duration, minimum R)

TABLE 2.
Results from 20 mm thick specimen with 4 layer skins

Position	Peak Force (N)	Pulse Duration (m sec)	Ratio, R. ($f_{\max} = 1.2$ kHz, $f_b = 0.6$ kHz)
GM	44	0.99	0.44
GE	43	1.05	0.42
LGM	40	1.05	0.42
1a	9	3.59	0.01
1p	16	2.09	0.31
2a	30	1.37	0.34
2p	33	1.24	0.37
2e	35	1.34	0.34
3a	30	1.36	0.31

TABLE 3.
Results from 3 mm thick specimen with 4 layer skins

Position	Peak Force (N)	Pulse Duration (m sec)	Ratio, R. ($f_{\max} = 1.2$ kHz, $f_b = 0.6$ kHz)
GM	42	0.98	0.44
GE	30	1.19	0.39
LGM	30	1.13	0.41
1a	34	1.19	0.39
1p	30	1.33	0.34
2a	28	1.27	0.38
2p	31	1.34	0.32
2e	21	1.82	0.28
3a	26	1.22	0.38

thinner skins. However, the predictions of Reference 4, together with the results obtained with the impedance method [5,6], suggest that this is unlikely to be the case, though since a given diameter of defect produces a larger change in impact characteristics when it is closer to the surface, variability over good areas can be less critical when the skin thickness is low. It is proposed to carry out C-scans of these panels using the coin-tap test in a similar way to that done with the impedance method [6], and the results from these tests will clarify the extent of the edge effects.

The 50 mm diameter defect, 1p, which simulates a defect with adhesive present which has failed to bond to the skin, gives a value of R which is much higher than that seen over the 50 mm diameter defect with no adhesive present, 1a. The reason for this may be seen in the time history of the impact over defect 1p which is shown in Fig 5a. It is clear that at the point A on the curve, the rate of change of force with time increases. This is probably because the impact has now closed the gap between the skin and the adhesive, and so the effective stiffness of the system is increased. This effect is also seen to a lesser extent in the results from the specimen with 8 layer skins shown in Table 1. It is unlikely that this phenomenon would result in a defect not being detected, but if necessary, the effect could be reduced by employing a lighter tap. The spectrum corresponding to the time history of Fig 5a is shown in Fig 5b.

Table 3 shows the results obtained on the 3mm thick honeycomb specimen with 4 layer skins. In this case, the values of R obtained above all the defects are lower than those obtained in good areas away from the edges of the specimen. However, defect 1a gives a higher value of R than that above the smaller defects, which indicates an increase in the variability of the test over thin structures. However, the defects are still reliably detectable, which is a considerable improvement over the results obtained with the impedance method [5,6].

Figure 5a. Force-time history of impact on defect 1p in 20 mm thick honeycomb structure with 4 layer skins.

Figure 5b. Spectrum corresponding to time history shown in Figure 5a.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that an automated version of the coin-tap test may be used successfully to inspect honeycomb structures with skins fabricated from fibre reinforced plastics. The sensitivity of the method decreases with defect depth, but the results obtained here indicate that defects 10 mm in diameter can reliably be detected under 1 mm thick skins. This suggests that the technique is somewhat more sensitive than the impedance method [5,6]. The results of the tests on the 3 mm thick honeycomb panel indicate that the technique is more reliable than the impedance method for the inspection of flexible structures. The extent of this improvement, together with an assessment of the severity of edge effects, will be clarified by carrying out C-scans using the coin-tap technique. This will be reported in a future paper.

The energy input to the structure during the tap is very small. For example, in the tests reported here, the velocity of the striker immediately prior to impact was 0.25 m/sec. (This velocity would be attained in free fall from a height of 3 mm.) The mass of the striker was 0.065 kg so the kinetic energy of the striker was approximately 2 mJ. This is much lower than the energy required to propagate impact damage in a fibre reinforced plastic.

The chief advantage of the method over higher frequency ultrasonic testing is that no couplant is needed between the structure and the tapping head. The technique is therefore particularly attractive for use in the field, and on honeycomb structures with thin skins which may be porous. The test simply requires the time history of the force input to the test structure to be captured, and this can be done via a transducer in the tapping head, so no transducer need be attached to the structure. Also, in contrast to the subjective version of the test, it is not necessary to monitor the sound radiated by the structure so the test is not sensitive to background noise. The proposed method for distinguishing defective areas of structure from sound regions requires the Fourier transform of the input force to be computed and compared with a standard from a good area of structure; with modern electronics this can readily be done in around 100 msec, so the commercially available version of the instrument, 'The Tapometer', produced by MatEval Ltd, achieves a testing rate of 5 -10 positions per second.

REFERENCES

1. Hagemaijer, D. and Fassbender, R. 'Non-Destructive Testing of Adhesively Bonded Structure', SAMPE Quarterly, July 1978, pp36-58.
2. Hart-Smith, L.J. and Thrall, E.W. 'Basic Principles for Tooling Design and Inspection', in Adhesive Bonding of Aluminium Alloys, eds E.W. Thrall and R.W. Shannon, Marcel Dekker, 1985.
3. Adams, R.D. and Cawley, P. 'Vibration Techniques in Non-Destructive Testing', in Research Techniques in Non-Destructive Testing, ed R.S. Sharpe, Vol 8, 1985, pp303-360.
4. Cawley, P. and Adams, R.D. 'The Mechanics of the Coin-Tap Method of Non-Destructive Testing', in preparation.
5. Cawley, P. and Nguyen, D. 'The Use of the Impedance Method of Non-Destructive Testing on Honeycomb Structures', in preparation.
6. Cawley, P. 'The Sensitivity of the Impedance Method of Non-Destructive Testing', in preparation.